

characterised as kaempferol by m.m.p., co-chromatography, microdegradation^{3,4} and spectroscopic examinations⁵.

Ethyl acetate extract on concentration gave a flavone glycoside, which when purified by column chromatography melted at 268° and analysed for C₂₂H₂₂O₁₁. On hydrolysis with mineral acid, it gave an aglycone C₁₆H₁₂O₈, m.p. 295°, and glucose. The aglycone has been found to be kaempferide (4'-methyl ether of kaempferol) by analysis, colour reactions, spectral data and preparation of derivatives. The glucose unit has been shown to be linked to 7-hydroxyl group by the study of spectral shift using aluminium chloride⁶ and sodium acetate⁷. The presence of glucose in the pyranose form has been proved by periodate oxidation and the presence of a β-glycosidic linkage has been confirmed by its hydrolysis with emulsin. Work on other compounds isolated from *Pterospermum heyneanum* is in progress.

References

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Study of Thallium (I)-Glycollate, Lactate and Mandelate Complexes.

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THALLOUS complexes with glycollic, lactic and mandelic acids have not been cited in the literature. In the present investigation author has therefore chosen these complexes for the study of their composition and stability.

E. Merck thalious nitrate and B.D.H. (Analar) glycollic, lactic and mandelic acids are used for preparing the solutions in double distilled water. Conductance measurements are done with "DORON" conductivity bridge with 1000 cycle WTW oscillator and dip type conductivity cell. Absorbance measurements are

done with the Beckman model DU quartz spectrophotometer using 5 mm light path absorption cells. All measurements are carried out at a temperature of 28 ± 0.5° and at a pH of 6.5.

The composition of the complexes are first studied by monovariation¹ method. 0.033M and 0.025M equimolar solutions were mixed keeping the volume of metal solution as 5ml and varying the volume of ligand solution making total volume equal in all the cases. Thalious ion forms 1 : 1 complexes with all the three ligands. The composition was further confirmed by Job's method² using conductance and absorbance as index properties. For conductance measurement 0.025M, 0.012M and for absorbance 0.05M equimolar solutions were employed.

The instability constant and hence the stability constant of the complexes are determined by Job's method². For conductance measurement 'P' (Molar concentration of ligand/Molar concentration of metal solution) was kept at 1.5, 2.0 and 2.5 with C = 0.01M. For spectrophotometric study 0.02 M metal and 0.05M ligand solutions were mixed, and for each ligand readings were recorded at three different wave lengths according to suitability ranging from 245 to 280 nm.

The values of dissociation constants both by conductometric and spectrophotometric methods are in good agreement with each other and are reported to be 2.11 × 10⁻², 9.22 × 10⁻² and 11.7 × 10⁻² respectively for the thalious glycollate, -lactate and -mandelate complexes.

The change in the free energy of formation of glycollate, lactate and mandelate complexes by the equation F = -RT lnK are calculated to be -2.299, -1.421 and -1.279 K. cal per mole respectively at 28°.

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Titrimetric Determination of Copper(II) with Thioglycollic Acid.

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A method for the determination of copper(II) in aqueous solution is described based on the titration of a cupric salt solution with standard thioglycollic acid solution. Cupric ion oxidises thioglycollic acid to dithioglycollic acid with the simultaneous formation of cuprous mercaptide^{1,2}. The latter compound